

Improving workflows in digital art history

Sharing annotations for patrimonial images segmentation and object detection

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Transformations, A DARIAH Journal Abstract

Volume 1, 2025

<https://transformations.episciences.org>

Dates

Submitted: 17/10/2024

Accepted: 04/04/2025

Published: 16/06/2025

DOI: [10.46298/transformations.14591](https://doi.org/10.46298/transformations.14591)

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This article addresses the lack of standardisation in digital art history, with a particular focus on image segmentation and object detection. It argues for the establishment of interoperable and reproducible data standards to enhance the effectiveness and replicability of current workflows. Through the case study of animal representations in ancient India, the article sheds light on the necessity of harmonising segmentation and object detection practices, while also taking into account the interpretive nature of art historical analysis. It advocates for the development of more adaptable tools that can accommodate the diverse levels of interpretation specific to artworks, thus facilitating the integration of multi-layered semantic annotations.

Keywords: digital art history, annotation, ground truth, computer vision, interoperability, standard, digital humanities, India

Vers des pratiques collaboratives en histoire de l'art numérique : le partage d'annotations pour la segmentation et la détection d'objets dans les images culturelles et patrimoniales

Résumé

Cet article aborde l'absence de standardisation dans le domaine de l'histoire de l'art numérique, en mettant particulièrement l'accent sur la segmentation d'images et la détection d'objets. Il plaide en faveur de l'établissement de standards de données interopérables et reproductibles afin d'améliorer l'efficacité et la reproductibilité des flux de travail actuels. À travers l'étude de cas des représentations animales dans les sculptures produites en Inde ancienne, l'article souligne la nécessité d'harmoniser les pratiques de segmentation et de détection d'objets, tout en reconnaissant le caractère interprétatif de l'analyse en histoire de l'art. Il préconise le développement d'outils plus flexibles, capables d'intégrer les différents niveaux d'interprétation propres aux œuvres d'art, et de faciliter l'intégration d'annotations sémantiques multi-niveaux.

Mots-clés : histoire de l'art numérique, annotation, vérité de terrain, vision par ordinateur, interopérabilité, standard, humanités numériques, Inde

Acknowledgements

The DARIAH Research Data Management Working Group (<https://www.dariah.eu/activities/working-groups/research-data-management/>) is a collaborative initiative that addresses the challenge of sharing and preserving research data in the arts and humanities. It brings together researchers, cultural heritage professionals, and data management experts to develop best practices, support open scholarly infrastructure, and facilitate access to data.

Funding

This article was written with the support of the Fonds de recherche du Québec- Société et Culture fund, under grant number 34639

Conflict of Interest

The authors do not have any conflict of interest to declare

INTRODUCTION

The study of a corpus of ancient sculptures using computational technologies places one at the intersection of computer science and the humanities and social sciences, within a discipline known as digital art history. Ten years ago, the very existence of this field was still in question (Drucker 2013). Over the past decade, however, digital art history has gained momentum. An increasing number of art historical projects are now applying methods drawn from the field of computer vision, confirming that the “pictorial turn” (Mitchell 1995, 540) has indeed occurred within the realm of digital humanities.¹

Despite these advances, digital art history remains a fragmented field: thus far, projects have not significantly interacted with one another and are mostly developed in silos. While European initiatives such as [Time Machine Europe](#), [ARIADNE-plus](#), and [PARTHENOS](#) are helping to structure digital humanities research, they have yet to foster significant cross-project collaboration in the specific domain of computer vision applied to art history. Projects that leverage computational image analysis remain largely isolated from one another, with limited interoperability and reproducibility among datasets, methodologies and trained models. Even the [Digital Art History Lab of the Frick Art Research Library](#), a US-based programme that specifically explores the application of digital tools to art history, often sees its projects operate independently of one another, without any meaningful cross-project collaboration. As a result, projects have rarely built upon those previously established.

This trend can be partially explained by the nature of digital art history, and digital humanities more broadly. By merging diverse disciplinary horizons, these fields sit at the intersection of two distinct areas of thought—humanities on the one hand and computer science on the other hand—each following their own epistemologies and methodologies. Interactions between these fields are still marked by a lack of mutual understanding between technical and “humanist” practitioners (Bode and Dixon 2009, 2). As a result, the solutions and tools developed are generally characterised by a top-down, technology-driven approach, making them relevant only to specific projects. This focus on the needs of individual projects hinders the reproducibility of workflows and limits broader applicability of the solutions produced. It also requires substantial financial and time investments, large amounts of data, and technical skills that are not accessible to all research units, let alone to individual researchers (Romein et al. 2020, 310). Moreover, it restricts the standardisation of digital practices, both in terms of data recording and model training. Notably, image segmentation and object detection, two fundamental techniques in computer vision that underpin many projects, currently lack standardised approaches and harmonised methodologies.

1. Some authors do not consider digital art history—and digital humanities more broadly—to be a discipline in its own right, but rather a set of (more or less) new methods (Bishop 2017). In our view, digital art history is defined not only by the use of computational tools, but also how these tools are implemented, opening up conceptual and epistemological reflections that transform research in both the humanities and computer science. In this sense, we see it as an interdiscipline (Beer 1996; Courtin 2016). This perspective aligns with the concept of “digital turn,” which not only introduces new techniques but also reshapes fundamental research paradigms and the ways in which knowledge is produced (Mills 2010).

This article explores how this lack of standardisation and harmonisation in digital art history hinders the reproducibility of projects and workflows, making them more time-consuming and less efficient. By examining the specific case of animal representations in ancient India, we aim to identify strategies to enhance workflows, making this type of research output more efficient and interoperable. The images presented are part of a corpus compiled for an ongoing doctoral dissertation on the iconographic and stylistic study of sculptures produced during the Indian early historical period (third century BCE–third century CE). These sculptures originate from various sites across the Indian subcontinent and were photographed during a field study in 2024. This research integrates computer vision through deep learning models for automatic pattern recognition and classification, thus adapting the workflow of art historical and archaeological analysis to incorporate novel techniques. First, a “typical” workflow in digital art history will be examined to better understand the role of image segmentation and object detection, and explore how these processes can be optimised (2). Next, the focus will be on the creation of training datasets based on artworks for computer vision models. There, we discuss the multiple challenges this process faces (3). Finally, the development of standards to address limitations in interoperability and reproducibility are explored, taking into account both theoretical frameworks and practical implementation strategies (4).

SEGMENTATION AND OBJECT DETECTION IN DIGITAL ART HISTORY WORKFLOWS: A CRUCIAL YET CHALLENGING STEP

Thanks to the increased power of computers and the development of large-scale research infrastructures, significant advancements have been made in the field of computer vision in recent years. The emergence of high-performance computing facilities and cloud-based platforms (like Google Colab, Amazon Web Services [AWS] and Hugging Face) has further contributed to its democratisation and widespread use across a diverse range of projects. Additionally, access to large-scale datasets such as ImageNet, COCO and WikiArt for art history and cultural heritage, has played a crucial role in training increasingly sophisticated models, thereby reinforcing this trend of democratisation and broad adoption (Cardon, Cointet, and Mazières 2018, 177).

Segmentation and object detection are two closely related processes that consist in identifying and grouping pixels in images according to areas of interest (figure 1). These areas are defined by the coordinates of their constituent points, which are typically recorded in a separate file—usually in JSON or XML format.² The main difference between these approaches lies in the granularity at which objects are identified: object detection typically generates a bounding box larger than the object itself, whereas segmentation creates a mask that precisely follows the contours of the object, thereby enabling categorisation at the pixel level (Dobson 2023, 84–85). Several approaches to segmentation exist. The most common one is called “instance segmentation,” which identifies and distinguishes each object in the

2. JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) is a lightweight data-interchange format based on key-value pairs. It supports structured data types and is designed for easy reading and writing by both humans and machines (ECMA International 2017). XML (Extensible Markup Language), on the other hand, is a markup language used to describe the content and structure of data in a document (World Wide Web Consortium 2008).

image individually. “Panoptic segmentation,” on the other hand, classifies all the elements within an image, including the background. The choice between either of these approaches depends on the specific research question and objectives. In our case study—the study of animal representations in sculptures from ancient India—we aim to analyse the form taken by different animals. Segmentation proves to be the most appropriate method in this context, as it enables precise tracing of the object and thereby allows for more detailed comparisons. Although segmentation remains particularly challenging in computer vision, it is nonetheless promising for conducting detailed iconographic analysis, for instance.

Figure 1: Difference between object detection (*left*) and instance segmentation (*right*). Lion; fragment of an architrave from the northern gateway, *stūpa* no. 1, Sāñcī, Madhya Pradesh, ca. first century BCE. Preserved in situ (*left*). Elephants in water; superior part of one of the *stūpa*'s slabs, Kaṇagaṇahallī, Karnataka, ca. first century CE–third century CE. Preserved in situ (*right*).

In a “typical” image analysis workflow, object detection and segmentation occur at two stages: during the annotation and during the training—and execution—of the model. In art history, this workflow can be broken down into six steps: image acquisition, database creation, image preprocessing, annotation, model training and performance/results analysis (figure 2). Multiple studies follow such a workflow to recognise, classify and compare iconographic patterns in images (see, for example, Lang and Ommer 2018; Milani and Fraternali 2020; Ghosh et al. 2021) or to detect and analyse the form, posture and facial expressions of figures in paintings (as in the works of Impett 2020; Sindel, Maier, and Christlein 2022). The identification and classification of artistic styles in artworks is also a recurring topic (for instance, Lecoutre, Negrevergne, and Yger 2017; Van Noord 2018). Most of these studies focus on painted works from the Western tradition, produced between the medieval period and the contemporary era. Moreover, although this “typical” workflow is widely adopted, variations do exist depending on the specific goals and methodologies of each project. Some studies rely on pre-existing databases, bypassing the initial phases of image acquisition and database creation (e.g. Zhao, Salah, and Salah 2022), while others forgo model training altogether and instead rely on foundation or generic models (e.g. Réby, Guillem, and De Luca 2023).

Given that annotation and training constitute the two critical steps for object detection and segmentation, we will focus our discussion on these aspects. In this context, annotation consists of creating images with expected results to generate examples from which the model will learn. Annotated data offers two key advantages: it allows researchers to specify the elements they are interested in, and more importantly, it enables better results with fewer images. This annotated data, referred to as “ground truth,” serves as a validated and reliable reference for training and evaluating model performance. Ground truth represents “true data”

Figure 2: Diagram of a typical workflow for image segmentation and object detection in digital art history.

against which a model’s predictions are compared, ensuring that it learns from accurate and well-defined examples (Sateesh 2021).

In the context of image segmentation, ground truth consists of pairs of images and corresponding coordinates that define the geometric shapes of identified objects. These coordinates are typically associated with labels that facilitate object categorisation. For instance, in the case of a bas-relief featuring two lions, the ground truth includes the image, precise sets of coordinates outlining the geometric shapes (also called “regions”) of each lion, and labels identifying them as such, thus ensuring that the model is trained and evaluated accurately (figure 3). However, producing ground truth is a lengthy and labour-intensive process that requires significant human resources. Additionally, it cannot be considered as an absolute truth, as it results from choices—conscious or unconscious—made by those who produce it. These choices are also constrained by the tools available, which impose certain limitations on the annotation process.³ While guidelines exist for some fields, such as medical imaging, there are no widely adopted, formal models of annotation specifically tailored to art historical and iconographic analysis, leading to further variability in how ground truth is constructed. Thus, the choices made to produce it can introduce inconsistencies and, in turn, bias the model’s training—a topic that will be explored in greater detail in the following section.

Once a sufficient number of images have been annotated, the next step is the model training phase. Two main approaches exist: training a completely new model from scratch or fine-tuning pre-existing models to adapt them to new data. In the field of digital art history, fine-tuning is the preferred method due to its many advantages: it provides significant efficiency gains, requires less data and computational resources, and consequently, demands a more limited quantity of ground truth (Wasielewski 2023, 103). This aspect is particularly important in our field, where models are not trained on millions of real-life (or “natural” images), but on smaller and more complex corpora. Indeed, cultural heritage datasets typically

3. Among the most widely used tools for image annotation, we can mention [VGG Image Annotator](#), [Computer Vision Annotation Tool \(CVAT\)](#) and [SuperAnnotate](#). VGG Image Annotator allows for basic categorisation and attribute assignment but lacks structured semantic modelling and ontology integration. CVAT offers little support for hierarchical or contextual relationships. Finally, SuperAnnotate is limited in its ability to encode complex semantic structures essential for art historical analysis. For a detailed overview of existing tools, see Kunwar (2024).

contain a limited number of images depicting complex objects and artworks, rich in layered cultural meanings. These features inherently constrain the potential for refining computational models.

Figure 3: An image and the coordinates of the identified objects, forming the ground truth. Winged lions; part of a frieze from the *stūpa*'s dome, Kaṇagaṇahalli, Karnataka, ca. first century CE–third century CE. Preserved in situ.

This is especially true when studying specialised corpora that are both smaller in size and present unique challenges. Unlike large-scale, generalist datasets like WikiArt or the Google Arts platform, which cover a broad spectrum of artistic traditions and periods, specialised corpora focus on a particular subject, theme, medium or historical time frame. These datasets require tailored approaches due to their limited scope and the need for domain-specific expertise in their analysis. In our case, the study of sculptures from ancient India presents specific challenges. First, the relief of sculptures implies multiple viewpoints and forms, complicating tasks related to image recognition and classification. Second, these artworks lack colour—often a key factor in object detection—and are frequently damaged or fragmentary due to their old age, further complicating computational analysis.

By their very nature, these specialised corpora require a greater number of annotated images and more extensive training to ensure that the models applied to them are effective and yield reliable results. Indeed, because they differ significantly from the images on which the models were originally trained, the fine-tuning method is necessary to ensure effective performance. Moreover, these corpora often require more than simple annotation; they necessitate the inclusion of semantic content. Semantic annotation involves the combination of objects with meaningful concepts or ontologies—such as linking a sculpture's depiction of a lion to a specific symbolic meaning or to a deity (Ponchio et al. 2020, 89). For instance, in figure 4, because the lions are coupled with a representation of the monarch Mandhāta, the semantic annotation would go beyond simply identifying the animals and link them to their symbolic association with royalty. The semantic annotation would also mention that the lions are the legs of the throne that the king is seated on (Revire 2016, 21). This second example contrasts with the bas-relief previously described (figure 3), as it introduces a deeper layer of meaning, emphasising the symbolic and contextual significance of the lion, rather than just its visual presence. This type of annotation aims to enhance interpretability and

context, rather than simply providing training data for model recognition (Croce et al. 2020; Réby, Guillem, and De Luca 2023).

Figure 4: *Mandhātajātaka* (Story of Mandhātā); middle part of one of the *stūpa*'s railing pillars, Amarāvātī, Andhra Pradesh, ca. mid-second century CE. Preserved at the Chennai Government Museum.

However, current digital art history projects often use models trained to identify objects in natural images, and then adapt these models to artworks. This method remains ill-suited for art history because natural images and their segmentation are not relevant to the specificity and diversity of cultural images.

CREATING TRAINING EXAMPLES FOR MODELS: GROUND TRUTH VERSUS A MULTIPLICITY OF TRUTHS

In light of these considerations, the most appropriate approach might appear to be reusing models already trained on cultural heritage data. In theory, fine-tuning such models would be more effective, as they have been trained on data that shares greater similarities with the target corpus. However, practical implementation faces several challenges. Firstly, there are still very few models specifically trained on artworks, and those that do exist are often tailored to highly specialised tasks. Secondly, the available models often suffer from compatibility issues at multiple levels (formats, tools, platforms), limiting their reproducibility. Thirdly, the heterogeneity of cultural heritage data and diversity of research objectives across projects further complicate their reuse.

The first challenge, which corresponds to the lack of relevant models available, is particularly acute when studying ancient Indian statuary: to date, no computer vision model has been trained on such corpora, as the automatic recognition of Indian sculptures is still an emerging field (Risam and Gairola 2021; Dalara, Sindhu, and Vasanth 2022).

In more extensively studied fields of digital art history—especially when compared to Indian studies—research projects have developed models that are sometimes

made available for reuse on platforms like GitHub.⁴ While this openness is commendable, it is impacted by the second challenge: the difficulty of reusing these models due to their lack of interoperability. Many projects are outdated and no longer maintained, relying on obsolete software libraries—especially when developed in Python—making them increasingly difficult to implement. Documentation is often incomplete, hindering both reproducibility and adaptation. Additionally, even when the models themselves are publicly available, their training datasets are often not, preventing any fine-tuning or validation on alternative sources. Legal and ethical constraints further complicate reuse, as many heritage databases are subject to access restrictions, limiting the distribution and application of models derived from them.

Such challenges to the reproducibility of cultural heritage data are not limited to annotation data and computer vision models. As Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra (2020) and Béatrice Joyeux-Prunel (2024) point out, the unique epistemological requirements and specificities of the humanities are in direct conflict with the application of the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) Principles to cultural heritage data. Challenges and limitations arise throughout the whole life cycle of cultural heritage data in various digital contexts, from its collection to its transformation into a digital object, as well as its management, analysis and sharing. To date, the majority of cultural heritage data, be it source documents, metadata, annotation data or computer vision models, remains difficult to find and access, far less interoperable or easily reusable. At a time when requirements for interoperability, reusability and reproducibility of research data are emerging as one of the ways of assessing the quality and scholarly legitimacy of digital humanities research, research communities need to critically engage with and address these persistent obstacles.

Beyond these two issues, the third challenge—namely, the heterogeneity of cultural heritage data and research objectives—ultimately relates to the problem of image interpretation. When producing annotations, interpretation occurs at two levels: a structural level, which concerns the form (i.e. the geometric shape) of the annotated elements; and a semantic level, where labels are assigned to these shapes to attribute meaning and significance. However, this binary distinction, in which only textual metadata is treated as conveying meaning, oversimplifies the interpretative complexity inherent in artistic production. Computational analysis often forces a rigid separation between an object’s visual (or “formal”) characteristics and its semantic description. Some projects have attempted to move beyond this dichotomy by developing computer vision methods that account for more nuanced aspects, like texture (for example, Mehri et al. 2017; Bianconi et al. 2021), but such initiatives remain rare and emergent. While texture, along with form and style—which are themselves carriers of meaning and shaped by socio-cultural contexts (Eisner 2003, 197)—can be characterised and described through labels, current annotation frameworks treat this information in a similar way to labels referring to the symbolic meaning of depicted elements, failing to account for the layered nature of interpretation.

Apart from this binary limitation, these two levels of interpretation also pose specific challenges. On the one hand, at the structural level, the same motif can be

4. However, it is important to note that no comprehensive list of such projects exists, making access to these resources inherently difficult (Kalliamvakou et al. 2014).

Figure 5: Battle scene; inferior part of one of the *stūpa*'s slabs, Kaṇagaṇahaḷḷi, Karnataka, ca. first century CE–third century CE. Preserved in situ.

annotated in several different ways (Miceli, Schuessler, and Yang 2020, 2). For instance, consider a bas-relief from central India where the goal is to identify and categorise the animal figures (figure 5). While the horse in the top right corner and the elephant pose no particular difficulty, annotating the horse on the left raises questions because the two parts of the animal's body are separated by the rider's leg. Should the entire horse be annotated as a single object, including the rider's leg? Or should it be annotated as two different objects, excluding the rider? Should the two areas be linked to the same object or treated as two distinct objects? There is no correct answer to these questions: the choice has to be made depending on the model used and the research question to be addressed. Moreover, most current annotation tools and platforms operate under a "one shape = one object" principle, preventing multiple geometric shapes from being linked to a single object. In the case of the horse, this means that if its body is segmented into two separate regions due to occlusion, the annotation has to include them as two distinct entities rather than linking them as a single object. This limitation becomes even more apparent when different parts of an object appear in separate images: existing tools typically do not offer a way to associate them within the same annotation framework.

One possible workaround for this issue is to manually edit the annotation file after export—i.e. modify the JSON or XML files—to explicitly link multiple geometric shapes to the same object, but this approach is labour intensive and prone to errors. Another solution is to use scripts to merge geometric shapes or to associate object IDs across multiple instances in order to indicate that two separate regions belong to the same entity.⁵ However, this method remains limited by the capabilities of

5. For instance, SuperAnnotate authorises the creation of complex annotations with relationships between objects, but multi-image management remains limited; VGG Image Annotator allows the

annotation tools, which must allow additional attributes or tags to be assigned to objects, and requires coding expertise and additional computational resources.

On the other hand, the semantic level involves adopting one of the multiple possible interpretations of a single work of art to create labels. Computer vision models trained on natural images do not face such challenges because they take a positivist view of images: a photograph of a cat is simply annotated and classified as “cat.” In art history, if an equivalent positivist approach is chosen, it prevents a more nuanced or multi-layered understanding of artworks. In fact, research has shown that a multiplicity of interpretations exists for each work (Leslie, Chua, and Jain 2007; Hollink et al. 2023). This problem is rooted in the concept of the “semantic gap,” referring to the difference between the represented object and the description that can be made of it, which is a particular cultural reading of the image (Arnold and Tilton 2019, 5). As a result, annotation and object identification are already forms of interpretation. They correspond only to one of the many possible levels of understanding (Panofsky 1939).

Integrating domain experts and researchers into the model development process through interdisciplinary collaboration is crucial for ensuring accurate identifications and interpretations of artworks. Yet, this is not always implemented in practice. Some initiatives actively engage with art historians from the outset, ensuring that the models align with research needs and methodological standards (Elgammal et al. 2018; Díaz-Rodríguez et al. 2022, for instance). However, many models are still developed from a primarily technical perspective, without prior consultation with humanities scholars, thus limiting their applicability to cultural heritage studies (Saleh et al. 2014; Crowley 2016). This lack of collaboration can result in tools that prioritise computational efficiency over interpretative depth, ultimately reducing their relevance for art history research.

In the case of semantic annotation, controlled vocabularies and ontologies are frequently employed to structure information. Yet, significant challenges remain. One major issue is how to establish meaningful links between annotated terms and existing ontologies, as most current tools do not support such integration. This limitation makes it difficult to highlight the layered nature of cultural heritage objects, where material, technical and symbolic dimensions are deeply intertwined.

These specificities related to artistic productions raise several questions as to how to process them computationally. Consider, for example, a Buddhist bas-relief depicting the Dream of Māyā (figure 6). In this scene, a woman lying down—the mother of the future Buddha—dreams of an elephant descending from the heavens and entering her side, announcing her forthcoming pregnancy. She is depicted in the upper part of the bas-relief, lying on her right side, her hand placed under her head. The elephant is in the centre of the panel, at the level of the dreamer’s feet. In this specific case, how should the elephant be categorised? Since it is depicted in a narrative scene, should the reference to the future Buddha’s birth be identified? Should its symbolic nature be specified? Or should it simply be categorised as an animal, like the elephants visible in the lower part of the bas-relief unrelated to this scene?

assignment of metadata to annotations, and can thus be adapted to associate several geometric shapes with the same object by customising the attributes.

Again, there is no unequivocal answer: it depends on the research question. If the aim is to study how animals are represented in general, the symbolic aspect does not necessarily need to be annotated. However, if the goal is to identify variations in their depiction depending on the context, or to highlight the plurality of symbols they embody, then their symbolic dimension must be taken into account. Current annotation tools require a choice between both options: they do not allow for multiple levels of semantic interpretation within the same dataset. This issue relies on a problematic epistemic assumption: namely, that images correspond directly to concepts and that appearances inherently reflect essence (Crawford and Paglen 2019). This limitation is critically examined by Balbi and Calise (2023), who argue that machine learning approaches rely on pre-imposed conceptual frameworks rather than emergent, nuanced interpretation. They state that, “For the machine, concepts like ‘style,’ ‘genre,’ or ‘subject’ (or even the idea of ‘levels of analysis’) are entirely surreptitious, technicians provide them with pre-packaged aesthetic concepts, and train them to recognize them.” (Balbi and Calise 2023, 6). This point underscores the limitations of current machine learning approaches.⁶

Figure 6: Dream of Māyā; part of the right pillar from the eastern gateway, *stūpa* no. 1, Sāñcī, Madhya Pradesh, ca. first century BCE. Preserved in situ.

Such an approach requires careful reflection: the annotation produced is the result of multiple decisions. Consequently, models trained on these data are inherently subjective. Reflections on this subjectivity should not be overlooked, as researchers must remember that annotations stem from specific choices and a particular interpretation of the images. As Dominique Stutzmann points out, researchers in the humanities and social sciences are under the impression that ground truth—and computer vision models more generally—is accurate and exhaustive, when in fact this is only accurate for certain specific research questions (Morlock and Stutzmann 2024).

Each research project in digital art history adopts a different approach and offers its own unique annotations and categorisations. There are legitimate and understandable reasons for this; yet the related issues contribute to a lack of consistency

6. It is important to note that while current annotation tools and computer vision models do not account for these critiques, a growing number of studies acknowledge these limitations, contextualise them and explore ways to address them (Impett 2020).

across projects, and to an unquestioned use of models trained on natural images. This prevents researchers from considering ways to improve model training and workflows on cultural heritage images, or exploring how to address technical challenges related to model sharing, such as projects that are no longer maintained, outdated software libraries and other compatibility issues. Most research focuses on improving models, rarely questioning the annotation process and the production of ground truth itself, despite its time-consuming and labour-intensive nature.

STANDARDISED AND SEGMENTED DATASETS: A SOLUTION FOR ENHANCING INTEROPERABILITY AND REPRODUCIBILITY IN DIGITAL ART HISTORY WORKFLOWS

Given the significant heterogeneity of cultural heritage data and the various ways in which it can be interpreted, achieving semantic consistency across projects seems nearly impossible. However, formal analysis—which relies on the study of visual elements such as lines, shapes, colours, composition, perspective and texture to understand how meaning is produced—can be normalised and homogenised, even though no standard currently exists for producing ground truth. For instance, the recording of objects' coordinates in an image, which is done in a separate file, differs depending on the tool used to generate these coordinates. It does not follow a structured and formalised hierarchy. As a result, if two projects employ different tools, it becomes impossible to reuse the annotations from one project in the other. Moreover, most annotation tools operate within a rigid framework, limiting the possibility of incorporating multi-level semantic analyses. Thus, we believe that improving the structure and sharing of annotations across projects, following standards that support structured annotations at different levels of interpretation, would significantly enhance the efficiency and interoperability of workflows.

Instead of sharing computer vision models specifically trained on artworks, sharing the ground truth for image segmentation and object detection appears to be more advantageous. Considering the wide range of possible interpretations for cultural heritage data, this solution seems to be the most promising way to streamline digital art history workflows and enhance their reproducibility. Establishing standardised and harmonised methods for producing and recording image segmentation and object detection data would make it possible for projects that share similar semantic frameworks to reuse ground truth produced by other projects. Given the wide diversity of research questions and study objects in the field, access to shared ground truth would enable researchers to extract only the annotations relevant to their specific needs, without being constrained by the original project's objectives. This approach would make it possible to refine models in order to identify one or more specific objects depending on the research goals.

The HTR-United project, led by Alix Chagué, Thibault Clérice and Laurent Romary (2021, 2022), focuses on issues related to automatic transcription of textual sources. It demonstrates the benefits of making ground truth openly available. Furthermore, as the authors underline, access to ground truth allows researchers to understand the annotation practices that led to a specific model, evaluate the results and even reproduce the model's training process (Chagué, Clérice, and Romary 2021, 5). By reusing existing annotated data, researchers can reduce the annotation phase in their own projects. This saves valuable time, alleviates what is often a tedious step and ultimately improves models and results, especially for smaller corpora, where

the quality of ground truth is essential to compensate for the limited amount of training data. The interoperability and reproducibility of data and models remain critical aspects in the fine-tuning process. Yet, this issue is left largely unaddressed. Current solutions are very limited and not particularly suited to digital art history.

HTR-United serves as a valuable source of inspiration, not necessarily to address the heterogeneity of data and sources in art history as a whole, but rather for its engagement in sharing ground truth. This approach favours the dissemination of heterogeneous data. It also makes research outputs that are useful for specific purposes available. For instance, if a project aims to identify representations of elephants in artworks, it can directly reuse the ground truth produced in our case study by selecting only the images featuring elephants. This flexibility makes it possible for researchers to repurpose existing annotated datasets according to their specific research questions without being constrained by the original project's scope.

In digital art history, the integration of annotated data in a flexible and shareable format like HTR-United is still a largely unexplored area. It must be noted that some standards for segmentation do exist, such as the [COCO](#) (Common Objects in Context) format developed by Microsoft (Lin et al. 2015). The COCO format is a de facto standard, established using the dataset of the same name. It defines the specific JSON format and categories that make it possible to label consistently and foster interoperability across different projects. However, these standards do not align with the needs and perspectives of art historians. The first issue is that their documentation is often very limited. The second issue is that these standards do not clearly define all possible forms of segmentation, which affects the production of ground truth. For instance, panoptic segmentation is not taken into account by the COCO format. The logic behind these standards is deeply rooted in fulfilling a positivist vision of object detection and segmentation in natural images. This focus introduces a bias towards a naturalistic interpretation of cultural heritage images, failing to account for their multiple meanings and the necessity for critical interpretation that we underlined earlier. The HTR-United project specifically aims to address these limitations in the context of automatic text transcription. What makes this initiative particularly valuable—beyond setting a standard—is that it was developed by and for a precise research community, tailored to its specific objects and scholarly needs. This is precisely the kind of approach the digital art history community requires today.

To address similar challenges in the field, a working group was initiated in the context of the Huma-Num consortium [Pictoria](#). It aims to develop a standard for annotations that meets the needs of researchers rather than being constrained by the technical limitations of existing tools. This working group aims to define a standardised and rigorous method for recording the geometric shapes and labels of annotations, ensuring consistency across projects. Furthermore, multiple, parallel and hierarchical labels, based on thesauri and ontologies, will be integrated into the standard to reflect the complexity of heritage corpora, while keeping a common foundation for ease of implementation.

For example, we might consider a bas-relief representing a winged-elephant inside a lotus flower. The diagram ([figure 7](#)) represents one potential way to annotate the image, using a standardised knowledge graph to distinguish between formal characteristics, taxonomic classifications and interpretative attributes. The terms enclosed in rectangles are sourced from a thesaurus, while those without rect-

angles are free descriptions. Arrows indicate parent-child relationships (e.g. “is part of”), while the equal sign represents a relationship of equivalence. The terms use the Getty Research Institute’s *Art and Architecture Thesaurus* (2017), while the relationships align with the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) developed by the International Committee for Documentation (2006).

Figure 7: Representation of a winged-elephant inside a lotus flower; middle part of a railing pillar from Mahābodhi Temple, Bodhgayā, Bihar, ca. second century BCE–first century BCE. Preserved in the Victoria and Albert Museum, London.

Following this direction, the working group seeks to establish a flexible yet comprehensive framework for both structural and semantic information, tailored to the diverse requirements of art historical research. The proposed annotation standard will facilitate data sharing across projects by ensuring both interoperability and analytical richness.

At the time of writing, the working group is still in its early stages. Several approaches are currently being considered, including the development of a cultural heritage extension for the COCO format and the creation of conversion scripts to improve interoperability between annotations from existing projects. One of the main difficulties concerns the creation of a platform for sharing ground truth across projects. Sharing images is a major challenge in digital art history, as they are often protected by copyright and require substantial storage space. A framework like I³IF (International Image Interoperability Framework) (2011) could offer a promising path forwards by providing a platform for sharing online cultural heritage collections.⁷ I³IF is an interoperability framework designed to distribute, display and customise high-definition images on the web. It is already widely used within the GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives and museums) community and facilitates image sharing through standardised manifests (Prunet et al. 2022). Images published by institutions with an I³IF manifest are accessible online via a unique identifier in the form of an ARK (Archival Resource Key). This system allows annotations to remain linked to the images through their identifiers when used for model training. This means that images do not have to be republished, thereby facilitating their use and distribution, and lowering storage requirements. Furthermore, I³IF is based on the Web Annotation Data Model (World Wide Web Consortium 2017), which

7. The potential of using I³IF to share standardised annotations in digital art history has been further explored in another article (Truc and Maronet 2025).

supports image annotation and segmentation with a dedicated standard that could be adapted for the standardisation of ground truth from cultural heritage images.

Despite its potential, IIIF currently presents several limitations for the sharing of ground truth. First, only images published with an IIIF manifest can be used, and no dedicated platform exists for distributing such data. This significantly restricts the practical implementation of IIIF-based workflows. In fields like Indian sculpture, for instance, no open-access, copyright-free, IIIF-compatible image repository is currently available. More generally, sharing images from specific, unpublished datasets remains a major unresolved challenge in digital art history. Although IIIF is not a ready-to-use solution at this stage, its interoperable architecture makes it a valuable framework to consider for the long-term sharing of cultural heritage collections.

CONCLUSION

Digital art history is a rapidly growing field with workflows repeated from one project to another, yet it remains largely fragmented. Most studies that address the improvement of these workflows focus primarily on refining computer vision models and fine-tuning generic models trained on natural images (notably Milani and Fraternali 2020; Shen 2021; Zhao, Salah, and Salah 2022). However, these models are not tailored to the unique characteristics of cultural heritage data and fail to account for the multiplicity of meanings that their objects can convey. These issues highlight the need for more reflexive methodologies in digital art history, where computational models are not merely trained to categorise but are designed to engage with the inherent complexity and multiplicity of meanings in visual cultural heritage.

Additionally, current workflows are lengthy and resource-intensive, requiring substantial human resources, computational power skills, and time. Standardising the recording of object detection and segmentation could streamline these processes by reducing the time and effort required for the annotation and model training phases. This would, in turn, enhance performance, especially for smaller datasets and corpora that models are less familiar with (such as the corpora of ancient Indian sculptures discussed here). Sharing ground truth appears to be a promising approach to improving model efficiency for segmentation and object detection in cultural heritage images. This method allows researchers to extract relevant elements for specific projects and offers greater flexibility. However, for this approach to be effective, the ground truth must adhere to standards and be available in an open-source, open-access format that ensures interoperability, facilitates data sharing across projects, and supports diverse research needs. Such a standard is currently being developed within the PictorIA working group. It aims to address these challenges and provide a flexible yet structured framework for the annotation of cultural heritage images. Ideally, more flexible tools should also be developed to accommodate varied interpretations, enabling the integration of multi-level semantic annotations for figurative objects.

The goal of this article is not to propose a perfect, ready-made solution. Rather, we have sought to highlight current limitations. As a conclusion, we would like to stress the importance of developing strategies to improve and streamline workflows in digital art history. While it requires further refinement, IIIF offers an interesting direction for future exploration. In any case, the GLAM community should ac-

tively participate in creating a solution that meets its specific needs and research objectives. Its involvement is crucial to ensure that cultural heritage data is not exclusively processed by private entities or confined to technical approaches that do not align with the field's needs.

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